

Flash Pulmonary Edema, as Collateral Damage

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Abstract

Three randomized controlled trials failed to show definite outcome benefits of percutaneous renal artery stenting compared to aggressive medical therapy in patients with poorly controlled hypertension, unexplained chronic kidney disease, or both associated with atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis $\geq 50\%$. Besides resistant hypertension and unexplained chronic kidney disease, atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis is a well-recognized non-primary cardiac cause of recurrent hyperacute “flash” pulmonary edema that percutaneous renal artery stenting routinely alleviates in observational studies. Other conditions than atherosclerotic renal stenosis may cause recurrent pulmonary edema although they do not present as acutely as atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis-mediated pulmonary edema presents. The findings of a positive, randomized, controlled trial of percutaneous renal artery stenting in patients with bilateral renal artery stenosis- or unilateral renal stenosis with contralateral renal impairment- mediated flash pulmonary edema may provide the needed support for thorough investigation and aggressive treatment of patients with flash pulmonary edema.

Introduction

The neutral findings of 3 major Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) in the management of Atherosclerotic Renovascular Disease (ARVD) considerably lowered the interest of the Cardiovascular Community for percutaneous renal artery angioplasty or stenting [1-3]. The prevalence of ARVD is 9% to 18% in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) and 25% to 42% in patients with peripheral artery disease. Patients with ARVD may present with resistant hypertension, rapidly declining renal function or recurrent pulmonary edema. In 1988, Pickering et al highlighted the hyperacute nature “Flash” of ARVD- induced Pulmonary Edema (FPE) and the major therapeutic impact of renal artery revascularization on the prevention of recurrent FPE in patients with ARVD [4]. Therefore, the greater casualty of the current lack of enthusiasm for renal artery revascularization is patients with ARVD and recurrent PFE.

After a brief outline of currently available FPE-related articles in PubMed, we review the presentation and pathophysiology of pulmonary edema in patients with CAD, left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, LVDD and mitral valve regurgitation. Thereafter, we examine the last decade's approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of ARVD.

Flash Pulmonary Edema in PubMed

Of 253 articles/case reports devoted to FPE in PubMed, 133 (52.5%) articles deal with renovascular disease/severe renal impairment, 48 articles (18.9%) relate to LVDD/heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF)/urgent HTN, 13 articles (5.1%) refer to Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) and 9 articles (3.5%) note mitral valve regurgitation. The remaining 50 articles/case reports mention a multitude of conditions with a $\leq 2\%$ incidence (eclampsia, pregnancy, ventricular, supra-ventricular arrhythmias, endocrine diseases or neurogenic pulmonary edema) except for iatrogenic causes of FPE (quinine, opioid, epinephrine, aggressive volume resuscitation) with an incidence of 5.1% (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Flash Pulmonary Edema.

Coronary Artery Disease

Extensive myocardial ischemia without myocardial infarction, that is not unfrequently painless, is a well-recognized cause of FPE in elderly patients with severe CAD and large areas of myocardium vascularized by collateral vessels [5-7]. Further, FPE may occur in patients with a large acute myocardial infarction caused by a saddle embolism into 2 branches of the left circumflex artery or in patients with acute myocardial infarction complicated by partial papillary muscle rupture and severe eccentric mitral regurgitation [8-10]. The cause of FPE was iatrogenic in a patient with moderate Aortic Regurgitation (AI) who received adjunctive treatment with an Intra-Aortic Balloon Pump (IABP) for hemodynamic stabilization before coronary artery bypass graft surgery for 3-vessel disease.

Regrettably, IABP mediated worsening of AI caused severe mitral regurgitation with pulmonary venous diastolic flow reversal and FPE [11]. Last, FPE may present with mild troponin elevation and EKG findings consistent with type B Wellens syndrome progressing to type A and severe distal left main and proximal left anterior descending artery stenosis leading to coronary artery bypass surgery [12].

In brief, CAD may cause FPE in elderly patients with normal LV systolic function, 3-vessel CAD, and extensive myocardial ischemia in the absence of acute myocardial infarction. Alternatively, ischemia-induced dysfunction of the mitral valve apparatus may cause FPE during an acute myocardial infarction.

Mitral Valve Regurgitation

Patients with ischemic mitral regurgitation and LV systolic dysfunction may acutely develop pulmonary edema. Importantly, patients with ischemic mitral regurgitation and LV systolic dysfunction usually have symptoms compatible with New York Heart Association (NYHA) class II-III at baseline; They may experience marked increases in mitral regurgitant volume and effective regurgitant orifice during physical exercise that precipitate pulmonary edema. Elevated trans-tricuspid pressure gradient and effective regurgitant orifice area corroborate the steadfast cardio-pulmonary process in patients with ischemic mitral regurgitation.

Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction

Two decades ago, Kramer et al reported the recurrence of acute pulmonary edema during an episode of marked systolic HTN independently from the presence of CAD or coronary artery revascularization in 12 patients with LV ejection fraction > 40% [13]. The recurrence of acute pulmonary edema and its association with marked systolic HTN in patients who had undergone surgical or percutaneous coronary artery revascularization led Kramel et al. to infer that tight control of HTN was essential for the prevention of acute pulmonary edema recurrence [13]. Subsequently, the same investigators highlighted the contribution of LVDD to the physiopathology of acute pulmonary edema in 38 patients with HTN who had no echocardiographic evidence of mitral valve disease, LV wall motion abnormality and LV systolic dysfunction during the acute episode and after treatment 1-3 days later [14]. Impaired myocardial relaxation as evidenced by a reduced early diastolic mitral inflow velocity was a pre-requisite in 37 elderly patients who were hospitalized for a first episode of FPE at the Mayo Clinic [15].

Nowadays, HFpEF is the most prevalent clinical manifestation of LVDD [16]. Patients with HFpEF do not commonly develop FPE (10) Left ventricular filling pressure (LVFP) increases at a steady rate over ≥ 14 days and at a faster rate in the few days that precede a hospitalization or emergency room visit [17]. Thus, the customary pattern of HFpEF decompensation does not fit the hyperacute course of FPE. While LVDD may contribute to the pathophysiology of pulmonary edema, it is not an overt cause of FPE. Hence, patients with HFpEF and recurrent episodes of acute pulmonary edema deserve thorough investigation [18]. Activation of the great splanchnic nerve may mobilize the venous splanchnic reservoir and increase left atrial pressure (LAP) by 7 mmHg to 14 mmHg in patients with HFpEF [19,20]. However, a LAP increase of 7 mmHg to 14 mmHg is insufficient to trigger FPE in the

absence of chronic LAP elevation. Unexpectedly, a recent phenotyping of acutely decompensated HFpEF does not include systolic HTN or CAD as phenotypes [21].

Atherosclerotic Renal Vascular Disease

Two-thirds of patients with ARVD have bilateral renal artery stenosis and one-third have unilateral stenosis with contralateral renal impairment [22-24]. However, unilateral renal artery stenosis can cause FPE in the absence of contralateral renal impairment. Renal artery stenosis reduces renal perfusion that stimulates release of renin by the juxtaglomerular apparatus. In turn, renin-induced activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system heightens sodium retention and intravascular volume overload. Renal artery stenosis-induced intravascular volume overload may lead to pulmonary edema in CAD patients with HFpEF and severe LVDD.

Diagnosis of Atherosclerotic Renal Vascular Disease

Sanga et al outlined a diagnostic algorithm for recurrent pulmonary edema in patients with renal impairment that combines direct abdominal Computed Tomography (CT) and renal ultrasound Doppler abdominal examination. The absence of right and left renal artery ostial calcifications eliminates bilateral ARVD. Conversely, the presence of renal artery ostial calcifications or a longitudinal kidney diameter < 6 cm to 7 cm with an unmeasurable renal Resistivity Index (RI) must lead to renal arteriography with minimal amount of contrast medium. A RI <0.55 or intra-renal RI heterogeneity alert to the presence of a significant renal artery stenosis that must be confirmed by renal arteriography. A renal artery peak systolic velocity >200 cm/s by Duplex Doppler ultrasonography correlates with a > 60% arterial stenosis. However, Duplex Doppler ultrasonography is technically difficult in patients with abdominal obesity, dependent operators, and can be falsely negative. The risks of percutaneous catheter renal angiography include local hematoma, pseudo aneurysm formation and arterial dissection as well as contrast agent mediated nephrotoxicity. Computed tomography angiography displays the renal arteries without the risks of arterial catheterization. Contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance angiography has the definite advantage of not exposing patients to iodinated contrast material or ionizing radiation.

Cardiac remodeling is more severe in patients with renovascular HTN than in patients with essential HTN of similar severity as evidenced by a lower LV fractional shortening and a higher LV end-systolic stress in patients with renovascular HTN. Among 467 patients with atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis $\geq 50\%$, 116 patients (24.3%) had resistant HTN, 46 (9.7%) had rapidly declining renal function and 37 (7.8%) presented with FPE while 230 (49%) patients had none of these 3 phenotypes. Twelve (32%) of the 37 patients who presented with FPE, underwent percutaneous renal artery revascularization. Over a median follow up of 3.8 years medically treated FPE patients were at increased risk of death or cardiovascular events while their counterparts with resistant HTN or rapidly declining renal function were not at increased risk of death or cardiovascular events. Thus, FPE is a major risk factor of adverse outcomes in in patients with ARVD. Subsequently, proteinuria was recognized as a major risk factor of adverse outcomes in patients with ARVD.

Treatment of Atherosclerotic Renal Vascular Disease

Recently, renal artery revascularization decreased mean 24-hour ambulatory systolic blood pressure by 19.6 mmHg, increased estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate (eGFR) by 7.8 mL/min per 1.73 m² and averted relapses in 14 of 17 patients with recurrent heart failure over a 3-month follow up in a Danish prospective cohort of 96 patients with severe renal artery stenosis ($\geq 70\%$). In brief, although it remains to be confirmed by evidence-based data, renal artery revascularization benefits patients with hemodynamically significant renal artery stenosis and rapidly declining eGFR in observational studies. Last, renal artery revascularization stabilizes patients with ARVD and recurrent heart failure independently from a FPE history.

Most patients with ARVD who participated in the 3 major RCTs of percutaneous renal artery stenting had resistant HTN or rapidly declining renal function [1-3]. In addition to numerous methodological issues including the severity of renal artery stenosis in the 3 RCTs enhanced adherence to medications during RCTs may have obscured the benefit of percutaneous renal artery stenting on blood pressure in ARVD patients and resistant HTN. The likely increased adherence to medications during voluntary participations in RCTs may have lowered blood pressure and the true prevalence of ARVD-related resistant HTN thereby masking the benefits of percutaneous renal artery stenting. Further, the 2 to 5-year duration of RCTS may not be sufficient to detect differences in hard endpoints like major cardiovascular adverse events in ARVD patients with resistant hypertension or renal replacement therapy or death in ARVD patients with declining renal function at an average decrease of estimated glomerular filtration rate of 5 ml/min/1.73 m² per year. In contrast to ARVD patients presenting with resistant HTN or rapidly declining renal function who are not at immediate risk of cardiovascular death when hospitalized for decompensation, ARVD patients with recurrent FPE are at immediate risk of cardiovascular death when hospitalized for decompensation. They are hospitalized in intensive care units and may require mechanical ventilation. Although ARVD patients with FPE are a minority compared to their counterparts with resistant HTN or rapidly declining renal function, the well-documented effectiveness of percutaneous renal artery stenting for the prevention of recurrent episodes of FPE may allow to collect positive evidence-based data in RCTs of smaller sizes than previously conducted. However, the main issue faced by investigators will be to enroll ARVD patients into a randomized controlled trial after the first episode of FPE that currently has a class I indication with a B level of evidence.

In brief, several observational studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of renal artery stenting for the prevention of recurrent flash pulmonary edema in patients with significant atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis. However, in the absence of evidence-based data and with the present lack of interest for percutaneous stenting of hemodynamically significant atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis, patients presenting with flash pulmonary edema may not receive the investigation and treatment they deserve.

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